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Author(s) — in alphabetical order		
Name	Organization	E-mail
Pons Nicolas	INRAE	nicolas.pons@inrae.fr

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Executive summary

This report aims to identify and suggest standards recommendations, best practices and recognized resources to appropriately deposit and share microbiome data and contextual metadata in public repositories with FAIR principles. Ethical and legal issues regarding sensitive data privacy in accordance with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) directives are also considered.

Report on interoperability

Introduction

In recent years, there has been an explosion of microbiome research with an ever-growing number of studies finding links between the composition of the microbiota and various states of health and disease. Microbiome studies have already delivered important insights into fundamental causes or signatures of risk factors for diseases, but we have reached a bottleneck: more sophisticated methods and a larger body of data are needed to unravel complex interactions and to account for known co-variables such as diet, lifestyle and chronic diseases. Currently, microbiome data and the associated descriptive or contextual metadata are scattered over countless small and large repositories worldwide, using heterogeneous (and sometimes non-standardized) sample processing, data collecting and analysis methodologies. Contextual metadata are often incomplete, inconsistent, redundant or not enough informative. Several studies suggest that metadata quality needs to be significantly improved. Misuse of ontologies or controlled vocabulary dictionaries can conduct to describe crucial concepts with dozen and more of terms (e.g. concept 'collection date' identified in multiple scientific publications with different attributes as `collection_date`, `collectiontime`, `collected_date...`) (Gonçalves et al., 2019; <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2019.21>). Moreover, data sharing in public repositories is a complex task with heterogeneous procedures according to microbiome data type (1) conducting generally to have data and metadata shared separately and not in consistent or unified repositories and (2) reducing interoperability (and more generally FAIR principles) across microbiome data. This clearly prevents effective sharing and collaborative exploitation of the data with innovative methodologies (such as artificial intelligence) or by performing integrative analysis (multi-omics and meta-analysis) to gain new knowledge and medical insights from microbiome data. Finally, a key challenge facing the microbiome research community is how to appropriately store and share the data and contextual metadata in order to integrate and interpret them in a FAIR way (i.e. in order to make the data findable, accessible, interoperable and reproducible).

To overcome these challenges, this report aims to identify and suggest standards recommendations, best practices and recognized resources to appropriately deposit and share microbiome data and contextual metadata in public repositories in an interoperable way. Ethical and legal issues regarding sensitive data privacy in accordance with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) directives are also considered.

FAIR principles

The FAIR principles provide a set of 15 guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of data (Wilkinson et al. 2016; <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>). The FAIR principles provides a useful framework for thinking about sharing data in a way that will enable maximum use and reuse. The FAIR principles were developed to:

- support data, knowledge discovery and integration and innovation both by humans and machines,
- support new discoveries through the harvest and analysis of multiple datasets and outputs,
- promote sharing and reuse of data,
- improve the reproducibility and reliability of research,
- be applied across multiple disciplines, even those that involve sensitive data,
- help data and metadata to be ‘machine readable’.

Through the FAIR principles, interoperability term stands for:

- (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
- (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

In that way, interoperable data should be combinable with other data from different sources by both humans and machines. To make possible interoperability, data should be stored in a non-proprietary open file format and described using a standard classification integrating controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, thesaurus and ontologies.

Standard recommendations to make microbiome data shareable and interoperable

Minimum metadata requirements

With the diversity of pre-analytics technologies and bioinformatics tools used to produce and analyse microbiome data types, it seems essential to describe with precision methods and instruments used, to ensure the best possible reuse and integration of data. It is recommended to describe data with enriched metadata using controlled vocabularies and ontologies as much as possible. However, finding the correct ontology for describing and

submitting metadata can be challenging. Some important web resources provide the relationships among standards, ontologies and schemas, the databases or repositories that implement them, and the policies that recommend them, e.g. :

- FAIRsharing portal : <https://fairsharing.org/>
- re3data portal : <https://www.re3data.org/>
- The European Open Science Cloud : <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

These resources should be used as a first entry-point to find adapted standards for annotating data and metadata.

According to microbiome data-types, well-defined standards are however fully recommended:

- **Metagenomics, metabarcoding and metatranscriptomics data types.** European researchers are invited to share and deposit their sequencing data on the European Nucleotide Archive repository (ENA), synchronized with US NCBI and Japanese DDBJ repositories. Data submission requires minimal descriptive metadata rely on a common data schema describing study, samples, experiments, runs and analysis. Submitters can use ENA default but poor checklist but in order to augment metadata richness and data interoperability and reusability, we encourage to systematically implement the standard called 'Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence' (MIxS) developed by the Genome Standards Consortium (GSC; <https://www.genesc.org/>) and validated by ENA/NCBI/DDBJ repositories. GSC provides the Minimum Information about Metagenomic Sequence (MIMS) standard designed for accurate reporting of contextual information for samples associated with metagenomic sequencing, and is also largely applicable to metatranscriptomics datasets. Furthermore, MIMS standard comes with a set of minimal required descriptors and with specific checklists depending on host-associated sample or host body site (e.g ERC000015 - GSC MIxS human gut, ERC000016 - GSC MIxS human oral...). Finally, GSC established other standards that are particularly pertinent for the microbiome data including the Biological Observation Matrix (BIOM) format and the Minimum Information about a Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MIMAG).
- **Metaproteomics data type.** The definition of community standards for describing (meta)proteomics data was initiated by the HUPO Proteomics Standards Initiative (PSI) (<https://www.psidev.info/>). In parallel, the ProteomeXchange Consortium (<https://www.proteomexchange.org/>) was established to provide globally coordinated standard data submission and dissemination pipelines involving the main proteomics international repositories (including PRIDE: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/>), and to encourage open data policies in the field. Submission guidelines and required minimal metadata schema are fully based on the standards defined by PSI.
- **Metabolomics data type.** Metabolomics experiments generally result in complex data to describe due to the diversity of measure instrument types (mass-spectrometry and NMR) and recent standardization

initiatives (Rocca-Serra et al., 2016; <https://doi.org/10.1007%2Fs11306-015-0879-3>). Main standards of the domain are based on vendor standards such as mzML or nmrML. Open standards such as ISA-Tab have been implemented to cover essential metadata, including experimental design protocols and samples and are required for submitting metabolomic data in public reference repository. ISA-Tab standard is included in ISA-Tools software suite (<https://isa-tools.org>). Application of these standards are required for submitting metabolomics data in the two main international public repositories: NIH Metabolomics Workbench (<https://www.metabolomicsworkbench.org/>) or MetaboLights at EMBL-EBI (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/index>).

- **Phenotypic data type (clinical, diet, life-style data...).** Formats used to describe phenotypic data accompanying –omics data are often heterogeneous from study to study. Even if some standards as GSC-MIMS e.g. can embed this data type, descriptors are usually manually defined by the submitters thereby reducing interoperability facilities between studies. Moreover, phenotypic data are often available as supplementary materials in Excel files or available only on demand. Reformatting phenotypic data of several studies to have consistent dataset ready for meta-analysis needs substantial investments). The initiative curatedMetagenomicData (<https://waldronlab.io/curatedMetagenomicData/>) is an example of phenotypic and metagenomic data standardization work. Regardless the data availability level, recommendations for study investigators should be to use recognized standards to describe and share when possible the phenotypic data. For example, for clinical data: SNOMED CT (<https://www.snomed.org>), LOINC (<https://loinc.org/>), FHIR (<https://www.hl7.org/fhir/>) (Martinez-Garcia et al, 2022 FAIRness for FHIR: Towards Making Health Datasets FAIR Using HL7 FHIR) or those defined by IHMCA WP1 (“Standardizing Clinical Metadata”). Furthermore, availability of well-described phenotypic data is crucial to conduct analysis in order to find link between microbiome composition and phenotypic traits. Study investigators should follow IHMS (International Human Microbiome Standards; <https://human-microbiome.org/>) guidelines to make available a minimal set of phenotypic data (as age, geographic location, BMI, basic health status...) in accordance with GDPR (preambl 35) on sensitive personal (health) data status and local regulation authorities.

Complementary initiatives have been developed to augment FAIRification of the data and could be implemented for the microbiome domain to improve data reuse and interoperability. EDAM (<https://edamontology.org>) is an ontology of bioscientific data analysis and data management (including computational biology and bioinformatics) and could be applied to describe in a standardized manner microbiome data life cycle and bioinformatics treatments. RO-crate (Research Object Crate; <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>) based on schema.org

(<https://schema.org>) is an approach permitting to package data with their contextual metadata, and bioinformatics analysis.

Finally, STORMS consortium (Strengthening The Organization and Reporting of Microbiome Studies; <https://www.stormsmicrobiome.org>) provides guidelines in order to standardize key information in scientific publications of the microbiome field. These guidelines (STORMS checklists) allow to identify required elements to share and describe in a standardized manner.

Data deposition in standard public repositories

Research data deposition in public repositories is crucial to :

- archive and share the data with FAIR principles,
- make the data reusable and interoperable,
- link the data with contextual metadata,
- attribute a PID (Persistent Identifier as DOI, accession number...),
- increase the research visibility,
- ensure transparency, reproducibility and integrity of the research,
- satisfy obligation of funders and publishers.

It is recommended to deposit data on recognized repositories. Figueiredo et al. (Figueiredo et al., 2017; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2017.00327>) propose the following checklist to choose a FAIR repository:

1. Does it require FAIR (meta)data?
2. Is it recognized by their community?
3. Can they restrict access to the data? (e.g., password protection)
4. Does it have efficient data encryption methods?
5. Does it provide good technical assistance and how much does it cost?
6. Does it curate their (meta)data?
7. Is their (meta)data citable and can they track usage and citations?
8. Can they link the data to another repository?

As mentioned above, web portals as FAIRsharing, re3data or EOSC can help to find a disciplinary repository. Concerning the different microbiome data types, following disciplinary repositories should be required at the European level:

- **Metagenomics, metabarcoding and metatranscriptomics data types:** European Nucleotide Archive (ENA; <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>)
- **Metaproteomics data type:** PRoteomics IDentification Database (PRIDE; <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/>)
- **Metabolomics data type:** MetaboLights (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights>)

To note the work of IHMCA WP3 to identify publicly unified repositories and resources for microbiome built in particular from these raw data repositories and providing summary data from microbiome studies (see deliverable D3.2 and milestone M13). These kinds of unified resources are key for the scientific community but need to deal with standardized and interoperable raw –omics data as much as possible. As an example of meta-omics interoperability success, the PRIDE and MGnify teams co-develop recently tools and pipelines for integrating metaproteomics and metagenomics data (<https://github.com/PRIDE-reanalysis/MetaPUF>).

Ethical and legal considerations

The data sharing policy is quite variable among the research areas and institutions. The compliance to principles of personal data and privacy protection sometimes leads to reluctance to share research data. Restricting access to data and their sharing prevents the re-use of the data, their integration with other types of data (e.g. in the context of multi-omics data integration), and to address new scientific questions augmenting the value of the data. There are several current issues and drivers related to the open sharing of research data. On the one hand, there is a growing recognition that data should be shared openly and transparently to foster collaboration and accelerate scientific progress. On the other hand, there are concerns about data privacy and confidentiality, as well as issues related to data ownership, cyber criminality, data sovereignty and intellectual property. Those challenges, which could be of ethical, cultural, legal, financial, or technical nature, must be considered when discussing the minimal data and metadata requirements for microbiome data sharing in particular concerning metagenomic data (and microbiome profiles) when coupled with personal health data and the risk to identify the person with health-predictive potential (sensitive data protected by stricter rules regarding GDPR). These questions should be addressed through research ethics committees, Data Management Plan (DMP) and risk impact assessments encompassing key points, for examples:

- Person individualization by ID (pseudonymisation),
- Human DNA trace suppression by a robust methodology,
- Masking of rare diseases and atypical microbiota,
- Categorization of sensitive metadata when suggested to be identifying (BMI, age...).

To address these challenges, several local and international strategies or initiatives are underway that aim at striking a balance between open sharing and data protection, and at ensuring that research data are managed and shared in a responsible and ethical manner. The EU has launched several initiatives as the European Health Data Space (EHDS; <https://www.european-health-data-space.com/>) which aims to create a secure and interoperable framework for sharing health data across the EU. However, an identified bottleneck concerns the integration of massive omics data (including microbiome data) together with health data. The actual initiatives are not ready to host, at a reasonable cost, such massive omics data. In parallel, several European initiatives are underway to develop standards for the integration of massive omics data and their sharing. ELIXIR (<https://elixir-europe.org/>) is a European organization that brings together life science researchers and provides them with data resources, tools, and infrastructure. Federated Human Data is an ELIXIR community that aims to facilitate the sharing of human data across different research institutes and organizations in a secure and privacy-preserving way. The community works on developing standards and policies for sensitive data sharing, building tools for data integration, and providing training and support for researchers. ELIXIR promotes several large initiatives such as B1MG (Beyond 1 Million Genomes; <https://b1mg-project.eu/>), GDI (Genomic Data Infrastructure; <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>) or FEGA (Federated European Genome Archive; <https://ega-archive.github.io/FEGA-onboarding/>) to create a scalable and secure infrastructure enabling federated access to genomic and related phenotypic and clinical data across Europe. Besides ELIXIR, EGA (European Genome-phenome Archive; <https://ega-archive.org/>) is an EU resource for storing and sharing genomic and phenotypic data from human and non-human species.

Summary of recommendations

Normalization, harmonization and standardization of metadata: develop robust and scalable metadata standards to ensure consistency and interoperability across microbiome datasets.

Adoption of data format standards to facilitate global integration and interoperability of microbiome data.

Promotion of data sharing and open access in accordance with ethic and legal regulation: strengthen data sharing policies, encourage adoption of FAIR principles, and develop infrastructures to facilitate access to microbiome datasets.

Development of interoperable tools and pipelines: invest in tools and analysis pipelines compatible with standardized data formats, using Common Workflow Language (CWL), focusing on technological innovation to address interoperability challenges (e.g. Galaxy, bio.tools (<https://bio.tools/>), WorkflowHub (<https://workflowhub.eu/>), BioContainers (<https://biocontainers.pro/>))

Encouragement of international and interdisciplinary collaborations: foster collaborations among researchers, institutions, and funding agencies globally to promote data exchange, best practices, and harmonization of research

efforts (e.g. ELIXIR Microbiome Community (<https://elixir-europe.org/communities/microbiome>), EMCC, MicrobiomeSupportAction (<https://www.microbiomesupport.eu/>))